

Rethinking silence within Arctic ecosystems

(with stories by Inger-Mari Aikio, Mathis
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Abstract

Building upon the acoustemologies of the Sámi – the only officially recognized Indigenous people in continental Europe – this article seeks to reconsider the ecologies and aesthetics of “silence” in light of the biocultural framework of Arctic ecosystems. The contents are gathered in a parallel plot of histories of listening from Indigenous and non-Indigenous stakeholders, from which distinct narratives of silence emerge. On one hand, silence is either presented as a hallmark of pristine, untouched nature, or a romanticized desert – both natural and cultural – echoing colonial ideologies of *Terra nullius*. On the other hand, within Indigenous acoustemologies, silence is indeed recognized as a distinctive feature of the Land, yet not as an absence of sound but as a state in which even the faintest of sounds emerges prominent and meaningful. The introduction of oversnow and all-terrain vehicles in the Arctic variably altered this multifaceted understanding of silence, as the article critically interrogates the responses of both Sámi and settler audiences to this loud anthropic sound source. Whether or not, paraphrasing Schafer, the sound of snowmobiles destroys a mystified “idea of North”, it is crucial to recognize that the same sound is also valued as familiar or even homely by Indigenous peoples who have fully integrated these vehicles into their traditional livelihoods. Using the anthropogenic noise of snowmobiles as a critical and counterpointal lens within Arctic ecosystems, silence is consulted through the perspective of Sámi acoustemologies, challenging the sonic colonialities inherent in top-down approaches to ecoacoustic conservation, and tracing the sonic reciprocities matured among people, machines, and other Earth beings of the tundra.

Introduction

In the pioneering book *The Tuning of the World*, published in 1977, soundscape theorist Raymond Murray Schafer states:

The destruction of the quiet northern winter by the jamming of snowplows and snowmobiles is one of the greatest transmogrifications of the twentieth-century soundscape, for such instruments are destroying the “idea of North” that has shaped the temperament of all northern peoples and has germinated a substantial mythology for the world. The idea of North, at once austere, spacious and lonely, could easily throw fear into the heart [...] but it could evoke intense awe, for it was pure, temptationless and silent. [...] As silence is chased from the world, powerful myths depart. That is to say, it becomes more difficult to appreciate the Eddas and sagas, and much that is at the center of Russian, Scandinavian and Eskimo literature and art. (Schafer 1977: 21)

Since this seminal work, studies in acoustic ecology focusing on the Arctic region often address the presence of anthropogenic noise pollution by oversnow vehicles, viewing it as disruptive to the conservation of a purportedly remote, natural purity and quietness of those places – a problem in need for acoustic regulations (Schafer 1977: 84-85; Baxter 1990; Farina 2014; Mullet 2014). Ecoacoustic analyses typically rely on quantitative data which customarily do not capture, nor even consult, the complex variety of acoustemologies that local and Indigenous communities cultivate towards the ecosystem they share (cf. Gieser 2019). While anthropogenic noise pollution by oversnow vehicles is indeed a growing concern in habitat preservation and especially in “naturalistic” destinations impacted by mass tourism (national parks, wildlife sanctuaries, forest reserves, wilderness areas), it is imperative to recognize the distinctive cultural contingencies where its measurement takes place. And while it is indisputable that the ongoing Sixth Extinction and the resultant biodiversity loss urge for global soundscape conservation efforts, the ethic and the set of methods employed in these acts of sonic salvation are only now starting to be critically addressed within the respective disciplines (ibid; Wright 2022; Kanngieser 2023; Kanngieser et al. 2024). Established ecoacoustic indexes and models often overlook the onto-epistemological diversity underlying the perception and use of certain landscapes (Novak 2015: 126), and this is where a biocultural consultation led by local histories of listening should be invited at the center of policy-making and academic discussions.

Building upon the acoustemologies of the Sámi – the only officially recognized Indigenous people in continental Europe – this article seeks to rethink the biocultural values of “silence” within the framework of Arctic ecosystems.¹ The contents are ga-

¹ In a different work (Renzi 2025b), I articulated the idea of ‘ecosystem’ (a wordplay on “echo” and “ecosystem”) as a complex network of sonic relationships, reciprocities and biocultural values that develop over time within a defined area, involving all living organisms, the abiotic elements that characterize it, and

thered in a parallel plot of histories of listening from Indigenous and non-Indigenous stakeholders, from which distinct narratives of silence emerge. On one hand, silence is either presented as a hallmark of pristine, untouched nature, or a romanticized desert – both natural and cultural – echoing colonial ideologies of *Terra nullius*. On the other hand, among the Sámi, silence is indeed recognized as a distinctive feature of the Land, yet not as an absence of sound but as a state in which even the faintest of sounds emerges prominent and meaningful. The introduction of oversnow and all-terrain vehicles in the Arctic variably altered this multifaceted understanding of silence, as the article critically interrogates the responses of both Sámi and settler audiences to this loud anthropic sound source. Whether or not, paraphrasing Schafer, the sound of snowmobiles destroys a mystified “idea of North”, it is crucial to recognize that the same sound is also valued as familiar or even homely by Indigenous peoples who have fully integrated these vehicles into their traditional livelihoods. Using the anthropogenic noise of snowmobiles as a critical and counterpointal lens within Arctic echosystems, silence is consulted through the perspective of Sámi acoustemologies, challenging the sonic colonialities inherent in top-down approaches to ecoacoustic conservation, and tracing the sonic reciprocities matured among people, machines, and other Earth beings of the tundra.

While this article builds on mixed methods at the intersection of ethnography and ecology, the methodological choices have been carefully designed to align with decolonizing research practices, ensuring an approach that is appropriate for a study conducted in collaboration with Indigenous peoples and grounded in Indigenous Knowledge. This includes the integration of Sámi traditional storytelling as a narrative complement to scientific writing, prompting the reader with a polyvocal intertext that reflects and honors Indigenous research co-production. In addition to citing oral teachings as personal communications (specified in footnotes), the text is punctuated with lengthier excerpts from *muitalusat*, or histories of listening, shared with me by three main research collaborators whose names are featured in the article’s contributor credits. Their *muitalusat* are published in full within the audio-anthology *Muitalusat guldaleami birra – Histories of Listening from Sápmi*, a collaborative artistic research project I curated as a multimedia output for my doctoral dissertation (Renzi 2025b). Each quoted passage from these narratives is accompanied by a QR code linking the reader to the precise timestamp within the online-published audio-anthology, ensuring that the research collaborators’ voices maintain their own storytelling presence within the article.

the ways they influence each other.

Jaskatvuohta²

Silence is one of the most recurrent and cherished features of the Arctic. While this is true for tourists and nature enthusiasts that visit this region yearning for a retreat from urban loudness to more tranquil surroundings (see below), in Sápmi, silence holds an equally prominent place for Indigenous communities, who experience it as an active component of local ecosystems – a medium through which relationships with the Land and the vitality of all its inhabitants are felt and expressed. In her contribution to the audio-anthology *Muitalusat guldaleami birra*, Sámi poet Inger-Mari Aikio reflects on a profound sense of belonging and homeliness inherent to silence, a quality often taken for granted yet one that resurfaces with renewed intensity upon returning to Sápmi after time spent away, exposed to loud, urban ecosystems:³

<p><i>Mun in goassige jurddaš abte dál mun guldalan, muhto mun libkká dan de dat jienat, dat mearkkašit hirbmat olu.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Dat bohtet de doppe gosnu.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ja, dat mannet mu sisa.</i></p> <p><i>Ja, go lean jodus erenoamážit, mun fuobmán abte, doppe lea menddo olu riedja.</i></p> <p><i>Ja, dát váikkuba munnje nie abte mu sisa šaddá dego dakkár čáhpes fápmu.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ja mun átestuvvan ja orru abte mun in sáhte leat doppe šat gubkit.</i></p> <p><i>Erenoamážit gávpogat leat dakkár báikkit abte dat lea veadjet-mehtun orrut doppe gubkit áigge.</i></p> <p><i>Dat orru abte dat garra jienat dego borret mus bihtáid bihtáid mielde.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ja go mun leamašan vahkeku gávpogis de orru dego mus lea jávkan juo oassi das mii mun lean.</i></p> <p><i>Muhto de fas go, ovdamearkadihtii boadan deike ruoktot Sápmat de mun čohkkán das olggubealde dat lea bieggá ja sáhtttá leat doppe beštor dahje sáhtttá leat rievssat.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Dat lea, dat leat jienat muhto dat lea ráfi jienat.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ja jaskatvuohta, dat bábcet millii dakkár bottut.</i></p>	<p>I never realize that I'm listening, but still I'm moved by the sounds, they mean a lot.</p> <p>They come from somewhere.</p> <p>And they are going inside me.</p> <p>Especially when I'm travelling somewhere, then I discover that it's way too loud.</p> <p>And this affects me in the way that... inside of me, it becomes like this dark power.</p> <p>And I despair and it feels like I can't be there no longer.</p> <p>Especially cities are those places that it's impossible to stay there for a long time.</p> <p>It seems like those strong sounds, they are eating me piece by piece.</p> <p>When I've been for a week in the city, it feels like a part of who I am has disappeared.</p> <p>But then when I, for example, arrive home in Sápmi, then I'm sitting outside here and there's the wind, and there could be <i>beštor</i> [<i>Motacilla alba</i>] or <i>rievssat</i> [<i>Lagopus lagopus</i>], birds of all kinds.</p> <p>And those are sounds too.</p> <p>But they are peaceful sounds.</p> <p>And silence, they all leave the mind in such a resting state.</p>
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The word here – and commonly in Sámi dictionaries – translated in English as “silence” is *jaskatvuohta*. This North Sámi term carries a semantic richness and complexity that extends well beyond the main English definition of a «state or condition when nothing is audible; complete quietness or stillness; an absence of all sound or noise».⁴ Rather, *jaskatvuohta* encompasses a multilayered concept across both acoustic and psychophysical cognition, referring more accurately to a “peaceful” state or condition when even

² “Quietude, tranquility, silence”.

³ Aikio 2025.

⁴ Oxford English Dictionary, s.v. “silence (n. & int.)”, September 2024.

the faintest sound becomes audible; a quietude that is not marked by stillness but by heightened awareness, where the subtle and nuances of presence emerge.

While the absence of movement may still contribute to the definition of *jaskatvuohta*, in Sápmi stillness never infers a total absence of sounds. It is for this reason that, for example, something as seemingly static, inanimate and silent as a rock can hold a distinctively dialogic role within Sápmi ecosystems (cf. Ochoa Gautier 2015: 189). In the case of rocks, stones and boulders – which I explored in a recent publication – this animacy may be attributed to the hierophonic presence of chthonic entities that inhabit these geological morphologies of the Land (Renzi 2023a). However, a similar acoustic vitality in stillness surfaces also when attuned to the rhythmic unfolding of seasons, where *jaskatvuohta* denotes a relational state for knowing the condition of ice paying attention to its (often quiet) vocal transformations:⁵

*Čakkat mun sáhtat čuččodit doppe jávregáttis, ja dat lea áiddo
jiekŋumin. Jiekŋui jo veahá ja lea jiekŋomin ja ássumin dat
jiekŋa.*

*Dat jienat mat das bohtet, dat gullo
dat “krakk krakk”.*

*Dahje dakkár bohkas go jiekŋa lihkada
ja šaddá ja...*

Dat lea imašlaš boddu.

*Dat lea juoga maid don it gula juohke beaivve muhto don
diedat ahte go čakkat manit lea skábman de manat dohko
jávregáddái don gulat ja dat lea hui fámoláš dovdu.*

*Dat lea áibbas jaskat, ja de lea fáhkka dat, dat jiekŋa dego
eallá.*

During the fall, I can be standing by the lakeside, and the ice is starting to form. The ice is forming little by little, freezing and settling.

And the sounds that are coming from that, sounds like “krakk krakk”.

Or like this grinding sound of when the ice is moving and developing and...

It's this strange tranquility.

It's something that you don't hear every day. But when you do, then you know that fall is here and, after that, *skábma* is coming to the lake too – it's a very powerful feeling to hear those sounds.

It's completely silent, and then suddenly, the ice is like it's alive.

...Even in the glacial immobility of *skábma* [polar night], *jaskatvuohta* is recognized as the “loud” and defining vocality of the winter season, as Johan Sara Jr. resonantly conveys:

Juohke áigodagas lea iežas ivdni ja šuokŋa [...]. Ja go lea 40 buolašgráda de lea duodaid jaskat. Visot dáin lea sin iežas mearkkašupmi ekologalaš dássálasvuhtii ja biologalaš man-nui. [...] Leat oassin eallimis man ealán.⁶

That *jaskatvuohta* is a relational condition towards faint and unheard voices is further communicated in the *mutalus* of Inger-Mari Aikio, in stark contrast to environments that either discourage or entirely prevent this sensory condition:

⁵ Aikio 2025.

⁶ [«Each season has its own shade of sound [...]. And the silence of -40 degrees is striking. Everything plays a part in the ecological balance and biological rhythm. [...] This is an important part of the world I live in»], from the liner notes of Sara (2010), also published online at: <https://stierdna.com/Releases/Earlier/transmission.htm>

<p><i>Muhtimat lohket sii liikojit leat gávpogis doppe dat lea dat eallin. Oh mun in ádde dán. Muhto dat lea diedus go mun lean hárvánan deike Sápmái ja dáppe lea nu jaskat. Dáppe don duođaid gulat dakkár áibbas jaskes jienaid maiddá. Gávpogis dušše dat garra jienat dat bohtet ja mannet du čada. Gii doppe gullá maidige dakkár áibbas smávva unna jienaid?</i></p>	<p>Some people say they like to be in the cities, because cities are so alive and there's so much life there. Oh, I don't understand that. But it's because, of course, I'm used to being here in Sápmi where it's so silent. Here you can really hear some really quiet sounds too. In the city, only the loud noises come and go through your body. Who out there would even hear any of those tiny little sounds?</p>
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Inger-Mari continues her *muitalus* recalling a listening experience that was particularly illuminating of how *jaskatvuohta* presupposes an attentive, almost microscopic listening, rather than a deaf ignorance that equates stillness with an absence of voices (cf. Ochoa Gautier 2015: 183):⁸

<p><i>Ovdamearkadihti das lea sullii vihttanuppelohkái jagi dassái go dat mádut borreghote dáppe min sođiid lasttaid. Jos gii nu livččii muitalan munnje ahte don sáhtat gullat go dat mádut borret lasttaid de mun in livčče jáhkán. Muhto mun čužžen dan muora vuolde, dan soaji vuolde ja guldalin. Dat orui nu imaš goal dat guldalit duháhat ja duháhat mádut borramin daid lásttaid. Sáhtat gullat dan. Dat lei maid imašlaš boddu. Muhto ii don gávpogis gula diekkár. Vaikko livččii olu mádut de mun in jáhke ahte doppe gii nu váccašii, čužžošii já guldalit go mádut borret lasttaid.</i></p>	<p>For example, it's been about fifteen years since the larvae started to eat our birch leaves. If someone were to tell me that you are able to hear those sounds of the larvae that are eating the leaves, I wouldn't believe them. But then I was standing underneath this tree, underneath its branch, and I was listening. And it was so amazing to listen to thousands and thousands of larvae eating those leaves. You can actually hear them. That was also strangely relaxing. But you don't hear that in the city. Even if there were lots of larvae, I don't think anyone would walk around, stand and listen to them as they are eating the leaves.</p>
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In her own *muitalus* from the audio-anthology, Sámi scholar Ellen-Johanne Kvalsvik also reflects on the sensory numbness that seems to arise from extended exposure to urban echosystems:

When you stop noticing the sounds, you lose a lot of information that are available around you, in the environment. I know that from living in larger cities, after a while you get a bit numb to the soundscape. It's all this noise, like a big river. I get very tired from these sounds. So to me they are noise.⁹

⁷ Aikio 2025.

⁸ Aikio 2025.

⁹ Kvalsvik 2025.

Now, noise is typically conceived as the polar opposite of silence (Schafer 1977; Sim 2007; Novak 2015; Kraugerud and Coughlan-Allen 2024). According to David Novak, it «is usually understood as a technologically produced field of sound, which is superimposed on a natural or social environment» (Novak 2015: 129; cf. Schafer 1977; Bijsterveld 2008). As such, within soundscape ecology and conservation practices, noise is understood as “pollution” that degrades the sonic balance of nature, compelling efforts for its mitigation and abatement (Novak 2015; Farina 2014; Renzi 2025a). Silence and noise, by their relational nature where silence is marked by sound absence and noise by sound disruption or excess, «can only take on meaning by signifying something else, but [they] must remain incommensurably different from that thing» (Novak 2015: 126). Thus, neither noise nor silence carries inherent meaning on its own; they are normative and relative to the specific acoustemology or auditory cultures that qualify them (cf. Malaspina 2018; Gieser 2019; Kraugerud and Coughlan-Allen 2024). Ellen-Johanne, drawing on her experience and sensuous ethnographic scholarship, pronounces on the relativity of aesthetic values correlated to what is noise and what is silence, noting that:

to other people it is comforting to have those [urban] sounds around them, because it is something they are used to. Soundscapes for people are probably very personal. It's how we learn to use the sensory system and what we sort out as being important and what we sort out not being important. [...] A friend of mine, that has been living in big cities all over the world, he tried to drive by car from Alta to Oulu and there is absolutely – oh, we cannot say “nothing” – but to him there was “nothing” in between, along this road. He got really scared because it was so silent, and it was winter, it was dark, and there were no sounds. So by not having these familiar sounds around him, he got very scared. That was a very anxious place to be in. He described that it is horrible being without sounds of other people – in the comfort of other people.¹⁰

This passage resonates with the insights of Ochoa Gautier, who remarks how the «identification of auditory thresholds changes notably from one culture and one living entity to another» (Ochoa Gautier 2015: 189). Here, the relativity of qualifiers like noise and silence intersects with the contextual and biocultural qualification of an ecosystem, underscoring the variability in aesthetic qualities within the sonic connections that individuals and communities cultivate with their surrounding environments (cf. Novak 2015: 127). In these terms, the absence of sounds can be an undesired condition that make the Sámi concept of *jaskatvuohta* inapplicable while, paradoxically, the perception of certain “noises” may contribute to define a certain ecosystem as *jaskat* [silent, quiet, peaceful] (cf. Kraugerud and Coughlan-Allen 2024). *Jaskatvuohta*, as emerges from Ellen-Johanne's

¹⁰ Kvalsvik 2025.

account, is shaped by the quality of relationships formed with certain sounds that acquire comforting and familiar values contextual to each individual or community.

Her own life story – as someone who grew up in a Mearrasámi [Sea Sámi] community – speaks about the cultivation of good relations with the loudness of motorboats that, rather than a disruptive and invasive presence, transmits to her a sense of place, safety and prominence within an echosystem that at once knows profound *jaskatvuohhta*:

I grew up, on an island, a bit out in the sea, where the seascape is dominating with the sounds of the ocean, sounds of different birds – seabirds –, the sound of the people moving, mostly by foot, not so many technical sounds, apart from boats, smaller boats and vessels. Especially these old wooden boats that have a particular sound, because they had this “totaktsmotor” [two-stroke engine], that is an engine going like: dun dun dun dun dun dun dung. That is very typical for the older wooden vessels from the coast. When the fishermen went out at 5 o’clock in the morning, I remember waking up to that and then I could sleep one hour before I myself had to go out and feed the animals. [...] I think some people think that noises of boats are annoying, if they are not used to them. It’s probably attached to me being a small girl in the fishing village, and knowing that when I hear this sound – all the boats going out in the morning and also when they come back – people are safe, when they come back. And for me this is the sound of people coming back.¹¹

Through the histories of listening shared by Inger-Mari and Ellen-Johanne, an attempt has been made to illustrate how the Sámi acoustemology of *jaskatvuohhta* diverges significantly from dominant interpretations of silence (cf. Malaspina 2018). While Inger-Mari’s *muitalus* provides insight into how silence in Sápmi is shaped by sentiments of peaceful quietude rather than a strict absence of sound, Ellen-Johanne’s *muitalus* expands this notion to include loud and often contentious technophonic presences, hinting that the evaluation of silence and noise cannot be universally reduced to excess of sound pressure levels or interference, but deserves a qualitative consultation of local aesthetics, ecologies and acoustemologies. This holds especially true in frameworks whose metadiscourse on sound does not differentiate noise as a general category, let alone binaries (Novak 2015: 125). Just like in the Sámi languages there is no word contemplating “silence” as complete absence of sounds, there is no single word that frames “noise” as a general qualifier like the meaning it takes in dominant acoustemologies.

The intimacy Ellen-Johanne draws with a “noisy” technological sound like the rumbling of a boat engine effectively echoes and re-aligns us with the loud, motorized subjectivity adopted as counterpointal lens within this article: the snowmobile (*mohtorgielká*).

¹¹ Kvalsvik 2025.

FIGURE 1. Digital scan of Sámi motorized and non-motorized livelihoods mirrored on Niillas Somby's *goavddis*.

The “snowmobile revolution” in Sápmi

The Sámi modes of land mobility relied entirely on non-motorized transportation, like skis and sledges, until the early 1960s. The introduction of the snowmobile presented reindeer herders with a new tool for covering vast distances and terrains more efficiently, and it quickly became vital to their seasonal livelihood, from the beginning of October to the end of April (Valkeapää 1971 [1983]; Pelto 1973; Helander-Renvall 2016). Beyond simplifying travel, the snowmobile «has also allowed for more permanent housing among reindeer herders, as they can reside farther away from the pastures» (Kuhn 2020: 23). These societal implications have not gone without internal debates and hesitations.

The conflictual imagery around *mohtorgielká* soon after its adoption in Sápmi is creatively demonstrated within the figurative apparatus of a contemporary *goavddis* [oracular drum] created by Sámi journalist and activist Niillas Somby. Among other symbols meant to prompt self-reflection on the most recent changes affecting Sámi society, the *goavddis* presents an image of a man on a reindeer-drawn sledge mirrored by a snowmobile moving in the opposite direction (Fig. 1). According to Ánde Somby's description of this image:

Niillas was a reindeer herder and he experienced those times when the snowmobile arrived to Sápmi. It was a huge transformation in herding technology here. From the soft technology of reindeers' sledges and skis, this motorized transportation took over. The figure alludes to the fact that this path may lead to the wrong direction.¹²

The peculiar iconography of portraying elements as doubled or reversed connects with the visualization of the *saivo* within ancestral *goavddis* (Renzi 2020).¹³ Some of the figures on Niillas' *goavddis* recall this figurative tradition, as well as the underlying oracular practice. The mirrored figures allow the consultant of the drum to discern between the different turns and challenges that the future anticipated for the Sámi in a rapidly transforming world. This visual symbolism reflects a polydirectional ambiguity in the ways the Sámi experienced this technological change, which moves beyond a smooth, linear

¹² Ánde Somby, Oral teaching (personal communication), June 11, 2021, Sirbmá, Sápmi.

¹³ The *saivo* is the upside-down underworld of the Sámi, reachable through bottomless lakes considered to be portals. In the *saivo*, everything appears to be the brighter mirror of what lives in the mirroring world.

transition to modernity (cf. Fraser 2018). A similar polydirectional experience resonates in the lyrics of *Mohtorgielká*, the 18th (spoken word) track on Áilu Valle's album *Viidon Sieiddit* (2019b). Set against a soundscape composed by Canadian-Sámi Raquel Rawn and incorporating snowmobile recordings by Jouni Aikio alongside drum samples from Niilo Rasmus, Áilu Valle presents the perspective of a «frustrated Sámi youth who is uncertain of the future of the traditional culture and livelihood» (Valle 2019a):

<i>Vai vel galggašii máhccat ovddežii</i>	Oh we should return to the old days?
[...]	[...]
<i>Leibat dat eallin nu ráhpa</i>	I wonder if the life was that good
<i>Ovdalge...</i>	Before either...
<i>Galhan mii diedus birget daid</i>	Well we do of course make shift
<i>veahkkeneavvuid hagage</i>	without the utility
<i>Vai birgetgo...</i>	Or do we...

Áilu's lyrics use the snowmobile as an emblematic subject that reflects ongoing crises facing Indigenous ways-of-being. Similar to Nillas' drum, Áilu identifies a pivotal *turn* around this technological entity, asking: once the Sámi adopted the snowmobile into their way of life, is it still possible for its use to respect the ecosystemic balances that have traditionally been preserved and passed down? Around this probing question, Áilu Valle contemplates:

I think nowadays a lot of Sámi have forgotten the ancestral connections with nature. It's really unfortunate, because the main reason can be found in the assimilation processes that Sámi had historically gone through. But on the other hand, change derives also from the connection with nature itself. Even though you can say that Sámi have a special connection with nature, the main point is that the Sámi have always been skilful in adapting, because nature is so harsh and challenging here in the North. It basically forced people to respect the environment and some of our contemporary choices also come from there. But when the Sámi have incorporated the Western way of living, and when life gets way easier because of technology, they tend to forget their starting point. It makes the process of forgetting easier and you get away from the circle of nature. In the Sámi traditional way, we take only what we really need, but I'm not sure if this is still true or not anymore nowadays. If I think of reindeer herders, now a lot of them have like three different big cars, two tractors, four snowmobile and as many ATVs. And it makes me wonder, is it really necessary? Is there anything left from the traditional knowledge? Because, in that case, you are definitely not taking just what you need, but you are competing against each other to survive.¹⁴

¹⁴ Áilu Valle, oral teaching (personal communication), May 7, 2021, Avvil, Sápmi.

While the Sámi recognize the continuity of snowmobiles in *árbediehtu* [ecological knowledge], when technology becomes an expression of economic ostentation, balances begin to falter (cf. Valkeapää 1971 [1983]). In the early 1970s, Pelto observed that snowmobile's introduction positively impacted the local economy, it also set in motion a gradual erosion of traditional social structures, fostering stratification and generating tensions related to economic success among community members (Pelto 1973: 67). This shift also heightened Sámi dependency on fossil fuels and, consequently, on non-renewable energy resources sourced externally. As Kuhn notes, extensive reliance on motorized vehicles has increased the Sámi's vulnerability to economic and political subjugation, with land use dependent on these vehicles often becoming a target for blame-shifting (Kuhn 2020: 35). This concern was also expressed to me by Áilu Valle who remarks how «the adoption a modern livelihood should not become a simple pretext for criticizing the choices of Indigenous peoples». ¹⁵ Once more, the frustration in the lyrics of *Mohtorgielká* effectively verbalizes these external pressures:

<i>Maid helveha don duodas oaivvildat</i>	What the hell do you really mean
<i>Dainna abte boazodoallu goarida eatnama</i>	When you say that reindeer herding uses up the land
<i>Seamma lábkai go ruvkedoaimba?</i>	And at the same time defend mining?
<i>Geahča daid proseanttaid</i>	Look at the percentages

In the context of *árbediehtu* and specific landscape practices, according to Gianluca Ligi, the introduction of the snowmobile led to a markedly different perception of time and space, as well as certain landscape qualities, such as snow consistency, ground conditions, animal presence, and herd management (Ligi 2016: 186). Similarly, Lars Johan Jannok (Juvve Biette Lásse) contended that intensive snowmobile use has contributed to younger generations of reindeer herders «eai dovddet eatnamiidda ge, goigo galgá mannat, gokte ealuin johtit ja goigo ealuin beassá»¹⁶ (in Skaltje 2005: 192). Remaining on landscape knowledge, Cogos et al. argued that toponymy «designating microscale features of the land, such as hills or rocks, are most at risk of disappearing, because the larger scale of travel using snowmobiles and motorcycles has made the use of such landmarks obsolete» (Cogos et al. 2017: 48).

A loud adaptation

In addition to these societal, economic and ecological concerns, the acoustic dimension of the snowmobile was not without its own set of criticalities. In relation to the just mentioned loss of ecological knowledge, a significant consequence of the acoustic in-

¹⁵ Áilu Valle, oral teaching (personal communication), May 7, 2021, Avvil, Sápmi.

¹⁶ [«lacking a deep understanding of the lands, where they move, how they move with the reindeer herd, and how to navigate with the herd»].

tensity of snowmobiles is the masking of other sound sources, previously essential in the development of environmental awareness and aural skills necessary for a safe navigation of the Arctic. Poignant verses (*dajabus*) reported to Maj-Lis Skaltje by Nils Tomas Parfa (Barffá Nils Duommá) vividly captures these sentiments of loss:

Hearggi luodi ferte juoiggadit juo muhtin áiggi
 Mon muittán iežan ránat hearggi
 Muhto ledje áiggit nu rievdan
 Ii dan heargebiellu jiena šahtin gula go ealuin vuolggát johtit
 Ii gula cussalusaid láidesteadjijn
 Ledje skohterat deid jienaid láhppodahtán
 Miesi itge gal juo gula go čohkkeme ledjet
 Oaidnima juo duogin dat lei goit¹⁷

Valkeapää underscored the psychophysical effects of noise from motorized oversnow vehicles, which often exceed 85 decibels, noting a concerning increase in noise-induced hearing loss (NIHC) due to these high sound pressure levels: «To tell the truth, our ears can't stand this mode of travelling, and all reindeer herders have suffered markedly impaired hearing during the course of recent years» (Valkeapää 1971 [1983]: 40). More recently, studies have examined the growing impact of noise pollution on reindeer herding caused by recreational snowmobiling associated with mass tourism, which, since the vehicle's introduction in Arctic Europe, has rapidly expanded as a profitable industry (Olsén et al. 2017; Kvalsvik 2019). Kitti et al. reported how in the Näkkälä and Sirkas pastures – where tourism includes snowmobile safaris – reindeer herders claim that even minimal tourist presence is «enough to disturb reindeer» (Kitti et al. 2006: 152). In a study examining reindeer responses to direct provocation by snowmobiles, Reimers et al. concluded that the sound and visual presence of *mohtorgielká* «appear to have little effect on ungulates in areas where drivers follow predetermined trails», though off-trail encounters can lead to behavioral changes, especially when reindeer are provoked and chased by snowmobiles (Reimers et al. 2003: 748). This very behavioral response to snowmobile sounds, however, was soon found to be an unexpected acoustic advantage in herding practices. Reindeer herders quickly realized that the loud humming of the snowmobile could serve as a strategic tool. Observing that reindeer, «scared to death of a noisy and smelly machine», instinctively reacted to the sound of the vehicle, herders could effectively use it to «chas[e] reindeer in the desired direction» (Valkonen and Ruuska 2019: 98). Tim Ingold notes that this strategy contrasts sharply with traditional methods of herding, according to which

¹⁷ [«Sometimes you have to joik the reindeer / My good reindeer is in my memory / But times have changed / When I move with the herd, I no longer hear the sound of the reindeer's bell / Nor do I hear the calls of the one leading the reindeer / Snowmobiles have extinguished these sounds / And you no longer hear the calf during the reindeer gathering / But it was still there within my field of vision»] (in Skaltje 2005: 92).

control was established by recognizing and taking advantage of certain innate characteristics of reindeer behaviour, such as the tendency to follow a lead, to bunch up when approached by a dog, and the attraction to the sound of a bell. Under the herder's control, deer moved at a natural pace. Snowmobile herding strategy is based on entirely opposite principles. Rather than following a lead, deer are driven from behind. Frightened by the noise and speed of the machines, they run in panic. (Ingold 1975: 3-4; cf. Valkonen and Ruuska 2019: 98)

While the loudness and speed of the snowmobile certainly provoke a faster pace and a more turbulent behavior in the Rangifer, it is arguable to claim that this strategy of chasing the reindeer from behind utterly opposes traditional herding principles. As I sought to demonstrate elsewhere (Renzi 2025b: 143), within the ecosystemic dynamics that set the reindeer in motion along their migratory routes, the mosquito – together with the wind – is ancestrally reputed one of the major driving forces. More precisely, ecological knowledge passed down through oral narratives and landscape practices assigns such a propelling role to *čuoikanieida*, the female mosquito, who perturbs and chases the reindeer from behind, driving entire herds to the top of the *duoddarat*. In this sense, though with far greater intensity and anthropogenic control, the snowmobile is fully integrated within the said dynamics; a novel and amplified buzzing that unsettles the reindeer, ultimately chasing them along an intended path. Curiously, this acoustic overlap between insect biophonies and technophonies was already noted by Schafer:

one general feature of insect sounds is of interest. More perhaps than any other sound in nature, they give the impression of being steady-state or flat-line sounds. [...] [T]he impression with many insects is of a continuous, unvarying monotony. Like the straight line in space, the flat line in sound rarely occurs in nature, and we will not encounter it again until the Industrial Revolution introduces the modern engine. (Schafer 1977: 36)

Echoing the well-known quote by Sámi linguist, professor, and politician Ole Henrik Magga – “the Sámi are the last to use skis and the first to use snowmobiles” (cf. Valkonen and Valkonen 2018: 40) – the chorus of Áilu Valle's album title track (2019b), which follows *Mohtorgielká*, recites:

<i>Mañimuččat geat ledje sabet alde</i>	The last who were on skis
– <i>vuogáiduvvamin, guorraseamen</i>	– adjusting, adapting
<i>Vuosttamuzžan skohteriin rassagohte</i>	The first who started working with scooters
– <i>siiddat duoddariidda dávisteamen</i>	– <i>siidas</i> reflecting the <i>duoddarat</i>
<i>Áibbašitgo duodas doložii go</i>	Do we really long for the past
– <i>vuogáiduvvamin guorraseamen</i>	– adjusting, adapting
<i>Go áiggít rivdet, de sieiddit viidot</i>	When times change, the sacred rocks widen
– <i>gilit odda dilis</i>	– the villages adapting
<i>dávisteamen</i>	in the new situations

As already suggested by the rapper in a previously mentioned communication, the core of Sámi culture – as also echoed by many community representatives across the four sides of Sápmi – is the ability to adapt and tune to transformations imposed by harsh environments, as well as other external pressures. In fact, one could say that the defining character of the Sámi is their seemingly relentless capacity to change while remaining true to themselves (Roué 2012: 49). Thus, despite initial reluctancies due to risks of “deskilment” and other degrading effects, as Valkeapää acknowledges, reindeer herders soon realized that their livelihood today «can’t be done without the aid of a snow-scooter. So we all have snow-scooters» (Valkeapää 1971 [1983]: 41). Snowmobiles and other motorized vehicles required adapting existing skills and developing new ones (cf. Fraser 2018). In this sense, Sámi scholar Elina Helander-Renvall emphasizes the benefits, acknowledging how, if in the past reindeer used to be frightened by the loudness of snowmobiles, over the decades they got accustomed when these vehicles are skillfully maneuvered by herders who attune with the ethology and with the responses of their herd:

it is a good working tool for transportation, driving and chasing the reindeer to a specific spot, and zooming around fast when searching for and gathering animals. It is time-saving which means, for example, that gathering of reindeer for round-ups takes place rapidly and that herders have more time for their families than before. According to the ANT approach, reindeer are also actors and influence the situation in a network. Reindeer are easily scared by the roar of the snowmobiles. [footnote: It has to be remarked that reindeer have become used to the noise of the snowmobiles, apparently because they (reindeer) associate the sound of the motor with extra food that herders bring in winter to them]. But reindeer tend to behave collectively in herds and follow leading individuals (reindeer) when chased or moving to a specific direction or place. These behavioral attributes make it easy to drive them towards a certain locality. (Helander-Renvall 2008: 30)

Thus, although this transition occurred not without nostalgia and regret for ancestral non-motorized methods, the snowmobile has ultimately integrated into the echosystem of reindeer herding (Figg. 2-3). According to Roué, particularly for younger generations who have grown up with snowmobiles,

their smell and their noise are included in his personal landscape. [...] And when they migrate, it is as always a close communion between people and reindeer moving across a landscape of known places rich with meaning, that today includes the snowmobile and its new noise. (Roué 2012: 48-49)

It would be a limiting assumption to consider these elements exclusively in relation to reindeer herding work, as they engage with and support a variety of livelihoods that include fishing, ptarmigan trapping and hunting, berry picking, or simply covering distances

to visit family or a *verdde* (Kitti et al. 2006: 147). This integrative role of snowmobiles and ATVs in Sámi ecosystems is nowadays recognized and safeguarded by national and international regulations. Regarding Sámi rights for traditional land use in the Finnish legislation, for example, these vehicles are mentioned as essential for the ecological and economical self-determination of Sámi identity and culture:

Sámiid kultuvra ipmirduvvo vuodđolága njuolggádusas viiddis doaban. Njuolggádus ii rádjašuva dušše giellaš vuoigatvuodaid dorvvasmahttimii ja ovddideapmái, baicce dat ollá vel viidasit dorvvasmahttit sámiid kulturhámi, masa gullet maid sámiid árbevirolaš ealáhusat, dego boazodoallu, guolásteapmi ja bivdu. Maid árbevirolaš duodji lea oassi sámi kultuvrra. Lassin sáme kultuvrii gullet maid árbevirolaš ealáhusaid dálá heivehanhámit. Dat, ahte sápmelaččat geavahit dán áigge mohtorgielkkáid dahje njealljejuvllagiid kultuvrii gullevaš ealáhusas, ii váldde eret dan, ahte sii leat eamiálbmot. Dán lea cealkkán maid ON olmmošvuoigatvuohtakomitea. Árbevirolaš ealáhusat leat sápmelaččaide guovddázis kultuvrras ja identitehtas nu ovttaskas go maid oktasaš dásis, muhto dat mearkaša sidjiide maid ruđalaš birgenlági.¹⁸ (Olsén et al. 2017: 123)

The value of technological adaptation in Sámi society is metaphorically summarized by *juoigi* and jurist Ánde Somby, who reflects on its constructive prominence with regard to the vitality Indigenous heritages:

In tradition there must be innovation. Innovation and tradition are the earmarks of a healthy society. If a society only has innovation and no tradition, then that society is like a goldfish that never remembers the moment before, and if a society only has tradition, then it's like a rock that just exist there, and nothing happens.¹⁹

The sonic relationships woven between people, reindeer and snowmobiles thus define the most contemporary horizons of a far-reaching biocultural heritage that, through adaptation and transformation, maintains vitality and an enduring fidelity to itself (cf. Harrison 2015). Inscribed within a shared set of ways of knowing, *mohtorgielká* elevates to subjectivity – a technological and ethical ‘first-person’ whose ontology and agency stems from lively reciprocities within the entangled spatialities and temporalities of the ecosystem:

¹⁸ [«Sámi culture is understood as a broad term in the Constitution. The Regulation is not limited to the protection and development of linguistic rights, but it aims to further protect the Sámi cultural heritage, which also includes Sámi traditional livelihoods, such as reindeer husbandry, fishing and hunting. Traditional *duodji* is also part of Sámi culture. In addition to Sámi culture, the current forms of adaptation of traditional livelihood also belong to Sámi culture. The fact that the Sámi use snowmobiles or ATVs in cultural activities today does not take away from the fact that they are an Indigenous people. This has also been stated by the UN Human Rights Committee. Traditional livelihoods are central to Sámi culture and identity both individually and collectively, but they also mean financial survival for them.»]

¹⁹ Ánde Somby, Oral teaching (personal communication), May 19, 2021, Sirbmá, Sápmi.

FIGURE 2. Early Sno-Tric snowmobile musealized at the Guovdageaidnu Riddu Duottar Museat.

A reindeer herder knows together with the collective of herders, with a reindeer, together with a fell and with a snowmobile, just like a *duojár* (crafter) knows together with the materials and techniques, together with ancestors and future generations. Knowledge emerges and is tested in active relationships, and a central purpose of this kind of knowledge is to ensure that life and living will be possible also in the future; it is not knowing merely for the sake of knowledge itself, but rather for the sake of responsible relationships. (Valkonen 2023: 9)

FIGURE 3. Lynx Forest Fox snowmobile musealized at the Anár SIIDA – Museum and Nature Center.

More-than-musical technophonies

The epistemological complicity of knowing and listening-with snowmobiles – as suggested from this last passage – opens the door to the discussion on the more-than-musical possibilities of *mohtorgielká*.

According to Sámi acoustemologies, anything in Sápmi – whether conventionally “organic” or “inorganic” – have a voice. Hence, *juoiggus* – more commonly referred to in scholarly literature by the non-Sámi term “joik”, is defined as the more-than-musical heritage of Sápmi; a highly sophisticated vocal tradition shared among the Sámi and other-than-human subjectivities inhabiting the northernmost regions of continental Europe. As such, it can be regarded as a biocultural heritage, since it does not operate within nature-culture divides, alien to Sámi ontologies. Within a previous study (Renzi 2025b: 10), I described *juoiggus* itself as an ecosystem, or a sonic network formed through performance, connecting individuals, communities and the environment. Any node of this network – whether a person, animal, place, or anything contributing to the vitality of the Earth – can be *juoiggalmas*, the source of *juoiggus*. Similarly, every node can be *juoigi*, the performer of *juoiggus* (Skaltje 2005: 255; cf. Buljo 1998). The link between two nodes in this network is known in Northern Sámi as *luohti* (pl. *luodit*),²⁰

²⁰ *Luohti* is the denomination pertinent to the North Sámi language and cultural region. Other denominations expressing the same notion – although it takes on different forms and contents – can be found throughout Sápmi: *luyvt* / *лывьвт* (in Kildin Sámi), *leu'dd* (in Skolt Sámi), *livde* (in Inari Sámi), *vuolle* (in

FIGURE 4. Creative schematization of the act of presenting through *juoiggus*: in this case, a human *juoigi* (on the left) gives voice to a *luohiti* (pitch contour in the middle) that makes the *juoiggalmas* (the wolf on the right) present (illustration generously contributed by Astrid Elizabeth Hakvaag).

and represents the vivid sonic presence of the *juoiggalmas* as captured and interpreted in the voice of the *juoigi* (Fig. 4)

For this reason, there exist *luodit* of persons (*persovdnaluodit*), animals (*ealliluodit*), landscapes (*baikeluodit*), wind (*bieggaluodit*), snowmobiles (*mohtorgielkáluodit*), and so on. A *luohiti* comes to the ear in the shape of a defined rhythmic-melodic formula, whose specific morphology ideally conveys the identifying essence of the *juoiggalmas* through an agile combination of vocal skills (Graff 1993: 399; Skaltje 2005: 286). Verses (*dajabus*) and transrational words blended together with the *luohiti* also contribute to the primary purpose of *juoiggus*, which is to make something or someone present (Hirvonen 2008).

Because of its relational nature and its quality to map networks between humans and environments, *juoiggus* represents for the Sámi an epistemological paradigm that “names” changes occurring in the echosystem, encoding them within a recognizable dynamic system of values, thereby expanding the same echosystemic network with new sonic connections, or *luodit*. Through this more-than-musical quality of *juoiggus*, the Sámi engage with change by capturing its essence and (ad)vocating it in the performance, and they can capture and (ad)vocate this essence to the extent that they reciprocally attune and listen-with it.

The growing repertoire of *luodit* where machinery, transportation and other technologies are the *juoiggalmas* signals a parallel, ongoing expansion of subjectivities in Sápmi. Through these unprecedented *luodit*, many *juoiggit* embrace – or in rare conflictual cases, exorcize – the “new” and make sense of its impact on a homely echosystem. Loudly projecting its technological voice across the tundra, the snowmobile has thus asserted itself as a soundmark defining the long Arctic winter. To the ear of different *juoiggit*, this

Lule and Pite Sámi), *vuöllie* (in Ume Sámi), and *vuelie* (in South Sámi).

FIGURE 5. Technophonic sonic mimesis visualized through a portion of the spectrogram from the snowmobile *luohti* joiked by Wimme Saari at the 2019's edition of the Ijahis Idja festival, Anár.

loudness appears a primary qualifier of the essence of snowmobiles. In fact, one of the few *luodit* I encountered related to this technophonic subjectivity plays specifically with voice amplitude in its sonic mimesis. In staged performance like the one I recorded at the 2019 “Ijahis Idja” festival in Anár, this expressivity is further emphasized through the mediation of another technological element, the microphone. In the recording (Audio 1), Wimme Saari joiks *mohrtorgielká* accentuating the loud and crispy roar of the engine by saturating the capsule of the microphone held on stage. Morphologically, the sonic mimesis also unfolds through gradual pitch shifts and punctuated breaks, vividly mirroring the gear changes and jolts from an uneven terrain (Fig. 5).

The sound of the snowmobile is conventionally sorted by dominant epistemological frameworks as a noise, an undesired sound «defined by its mutual exclusion from the category of music» (Novak 2015: 126). In light of this exclusion, listening-with the bio(techno)cultural counter-narrative at the foundation of Sámi more-than-music might offer alternative teachings for a broader, more meaningful and serious inclusion of diverse voices – including technological – in the global debate on musicality and sound ecologies. As Dylan Robinson provocatively suggests, if we attend «to affect alongside normative listening habits and biases», this more intimate listening positionality «allows us to imagine (or audiate) otherwise» (Robinson 2020: 38). Although, during my fieldwork, I have not personally heard anyone explicitly refer to the snowmobile as a *juoigi*, both Mai Britt Utsi and Johan Sara Jr., in mimicking the sound of the vehicle, employed vocal techniques reminiscent of *juoiggus* – much like they did for other other-than-human subjectivities like the wind or the mosquito that, instead, are acknowledged as other-than-human *juoigit* (Renzi 2024, 2025b).

On the role of the snowmobile as *juoiggaha* – a catalyst for *luodit* – *juoigi* and reindeer herder Olof Blind (Bolnnu Ovlá) describes to Maj-Lis Skaltje how,

Dál ná skohteráigge mon láven álo juoigat go mon bohccuid vuoján. Nu guhká go dat manná buorit, dat manná nu fiddnát. ležat jalgii goit orru nu finna luohti boahtime. Dasa gávdná nu olu sániid, maid ii dábálaččat jurddet ollenge. (in Skaltje 2005: 216)²¹

²¹ [«Now, during snowmobile times, I always joik when I'm driving after the reindeer. As long as things

Comparably, a reindeer herder from the Guovdageaidnu municipality told me that when she follows the reindeer on the *duoddarat* with her snowmobile, the engine of the vehicle occasionally provides a droning sound which triggers the spontaneous performance of *juoiggus* (Renzi 2023b: 168).²² Although predominantly referring to the sound of motorboats, Mai Britt Utsi also convened that if one listens-with motorized sounds, these may supply our voice with an almost boundless source of *luodit*:

<i>Je de iešgudetlagan sáhttan máksin heargi, biila, fanas.</i>	You pay attention to different things, a draft reindeer, a car, a boat.
<i>Na juohkelágan mainna jobttá olmmoš, dat lea hui na juigalaš dat ahte go don vuoijat go gulat motovra jiena.</i>	All kind of things with which people move, they are very “joikable”, like when you drive and hear the sound of the engine. ²³

On similar lines, Aubinet offers stimulating considerations on the role of transports as catalysts of *juoiggus*:

As far as I can tell, the only human-made things that people commonly joik are cars and snowmobiles, although these are rare sources in comparison to animals, places, and people. It may be that a guiding principle for what can be joiked is movement: people, animals, vehicles, and landscapes are engaged by moving through the land, whereas institutions or cell phones may be considered more static. (Aubinet 2020: 20)

Although Mai-Britt Utsi’s sensitivity to the sound of motorized vehicles seems to lend support to this theory, I find it crucial to recognize that while movement can indeed catalyze *juoiggus*, the stillness of the *juoiggalmas* does not inherently reduce its capacity to *juoiggaha* – as mountains and rocks, despite their stillness and apparent silence, continue to sustain *luohti* and inspire Sámi to joik (Renzi 2023a).²⁴ Just as stillness in Sápmi does not equate with absence of sounds or voices (see above), it should not be seen as limiting the power of any entity to joik, to be joiked or to sustain *juoiggus*. I argue that the greater incidence of snowmobiles on *juoiggus*, over that of other modern technologies, rather reflects the positive relationship – almost a ‘kinship’ – cultivated with this subjectivity and its respected integration into the traditional echosystems where *juoiggus* thrives. The absence of wind turbine *luodit*, for instance, may not necessarily be due to their stationary nature, as opposed to the inherent mobility of snowmobiles. Rather, it accounts for the constructive role that snowmobiles play

go smoothly, the *luohti* also sounds beautiful. In my opinion, a nice *luohti* comes. You find many words for the *luohti* that you usually don’t even think about»].

²² This was also mentioned to me by Sámi *juoigut* and musicians Hilda Länsman and Lávre Johan Eira, Oral teachings (personal communications), February 4, 2023, Guovdageaidnu. A similar account is reported in Driver (2012: 11).

²³ Mai Britt Utsi, Oral teachings (personal communications), August 15, 2023, Guovdageaidnu.

²⁴ Ánde Somby, Oral teaching (personal communication), June 11, 2021, Sirbmá, Sápmi.

in the reindeer herding ecosystem, supporting and driving the reindeer along ancestral trails, in contrast with the negative impact of the sound of wind turbines that, circumvented by the herd, disorients the reindeer and poses a threat not only to their survival but, by extension, to the ecosystem as a whole (Skarin et al. 2018; Oestmoen 2023; cf. Renzi 2024).

In these terms, I argue that beyond taking on more-than-musical qualities, the loud sound of the snowmobile – much like those of motorboats previously invoked in Ellen-Johanne Kvalsvik’s *muitalus* – becomes, for some people in Sápmi, a familiar presence and a vital constituent of *jaskatvuohhta*: a quietude relationally defined by an affective listening that transcends sound amplitude and rather cultivates attunement to the intense expressiveness of even the faintest whispers and finds quiet comfort in even the loudest “noises”. Finally bringing *mohtorgielká* into the conversation, the *muitalus* shared by Mathis Eira in the audio-anthology encapsulates this defining quality of listening-with affection:²⁵

Olmmoš de gárvodit ja geahččá dušše ohccat jienaid maid addet buoriid. Olmmoš haliidá gávdnot dego oadjebasvuohhta juohke dinga mas gullá dego.

Dego oahpesolbmotjienaid, dat addet oadjebasvuohhta. Ja iežan olmmoš jietnat, bearašša. Ja diedusge mu oktavuodas gal leat daid guokte jietna; eatni dahje luohiti dahje eatni go juoigá ja maiddái bohccut-jieanat, go lean bajašadden bohccuidguin ja mun dovddan ahte mun oaččun diekkár dovddu dego ahte mun lean ruovttus. Da leat goit dan maid mun dovddan. Mun jáhkkan da leat aistton, jus mun dajan dál ahte mun ii beasse goassege gullat bohccuidjietnat, mun jáhkkan ahte de gabče olu oadjebasvuohhá ja dat dovddu ahte don leat ruovttus, da gabče hui olu eret.

Dat lea aistton dan maid olmmoš dovdda, da leat aistton dan.

maid olmmoš háliida guldalit.

Olmmoš oačču aistton dán dovddu ahte lea oadjebasvuohhta, da leat ruoktu ja da leat aistton dan man ohcalat dego dan bade go eará jietnat mat dego, dat eai leat nu vuohkasi gullat dege addá dege hui unohas det olmmoš garvanit deidda diedusge nu ahte.

Nu ahte mun jáhkkan ahte da leat aistton vuos makkár jienaide, makkár oktavuohhta don čanat dan jiena maid mun jurdašan nu ahte, da lea muhtun jienaid mat muhtimiidda leat hui debalaš ja muhtimiidda leat eará jienaid mat leat hui debalačcat.

Ovdamearkka dihte muhtin liiko scooterjienaid ainna daid liikojit scooteriin, ja ainna daid čatnet dasa buori oktavuohhta.

Nu ahte da leat diedusge duovduid maid leat hui olu čatnun dieidda jienaide

People look for the sounds that transmit good feelings. People want to find, like, safety in everything they hear.

Like the sounds of familiar people, they bring safety. The sounds of your own people, your family. And in my case I feel certainly connected with two sounds: these are the sound of my mother when she joiks and the sounds of reindeer. Because I grew up with reindeers and when I hear them I get the feeling of being home. At least, this is what I feel. I believe that if I now say that I will never hear reindeer-sounds again, much of that feeling of safeness would fade away.

I wouldn't feel home anymore.

It is what people feels connected to...

That is what people want to listen.

You get the feeling you are safe, that you are home. That this is what you are looking for.

While for other sounds, like hose that

are not so good to hear, that are very unpleasant, people certainly avoid them.

I believe it depends on what kind of sounds, what kind of relationship you create with the sound.

There are some sounds that matter more to some people and other sounds that are more important to others. For example, some people enjoy the sound of snowmobiles because they weave good relations with the scooter. So those are feelings that are very much connected with the sounds.

²⁵ Eira (Mathis) 2025.

In his contribution, while discussing the affective values inherent to the reindeer herding echosystem, Mathis Eira underscores the sense of safety [*oadjebasvuohtá*] and positive connection [*oktavuohta*] that the sounds of snowmobile may signify to some. Since their introduction in the 1960s, snowmobiles have played an indispensable role in Sámi traditional land management practices. They proved remarkably valuable in reindeer husbandry, as this crucial profession required – and in some cases still requires – entire families to be constantly on the move throughout the polar year. The stories shared within the audio-anthology, along with numerous fieldwork accounts, reveal that the sounds of snowmobiles and ATVs are not merely tolerated, yet often perceived as aesthetically pleasant or even “therapeutic”, evoking a sense of homeliness and contributing to a local sense of place. Mathis Eira’s *muitalus*, therefore, speaks to issues of acoustic tolerance and significance, as well as biocultural sustainability. In doing so, it shows affinities with the message in Áilu Valle’s *Mohtorgielká*, which advocates for the Sámi right to decide on their own matters, in reconciling ancestral knowledge with this technological subjectivities for the pursuit of upholding traditional livelihoods.²⁶ Incidentally, it also advances a response to Schafer’s quote from the article’s opening, cautioning about how sounds that certain people consider to be noise, might be pleasant or even vital for others.

There is something both grotesque and fetishistic in Schafer’s *acoustemocentric* preoccupation with Arctic “soundscapes”. Is the snowmobile, integrated into the traditional landscape practices and ecosystemic balance of Sápmi, truly “chasing silence” from this world? Whose “silence” and whose “idea of North” is shattered or offended by these intentional adaptations on Indigenous lands? The ‘risk of deafness’ posed by the loudness of these motorized vehicles is antithetically mirrored by the ‘risk of deafness’ towards multiple, co-existing *ideas* of the North, which resist being singularly defined and universalized.

<i>Diktibehtet min leat ráfis</i>	Let us be in peace
<i>Eat mii leat dis doalvumin maidege</i>	We are not taking anything from you
<i>[...]</i>	[...]
<i>Dál sii vigget mearridit min áššiin..</i>	Now they are governing our issues...
<i>Min áššiin mearrida luondu</i>	Nature governs our issues
<i>Min áššiin mearrida boazu</i>	Reindeer governs our issues
<i>Min áššiin galgat beassat mii ieža mearridit</i>	Our issues must be governed by ourselves
<i>Danin go mii leat maid luondu.</i>	Because we are Nature too. ²⁷

Post scriptum

Today, I have found silence in Sápmi. After months of learning that this condition does not truly belong to these lands – despite the enduring settler imagery that paint it as a

²⁶ Áilu Valle, oral teaching (personal communication), May 7, 2021, Avvil, Sápmi.

²⁷ Valle 2019a.

synonym of vast emptiness and terra *nullius* – there it was, unmistakably before me: silence and desert. Moments earlier, I had been hiking through the dense, chirping forest along the Airvaaravägen after parking my car on the side of the E45. Majestic Scots pines (*Beahci*; *Pinus sylvestris*) creaked and swayed in the wind, raindrops trickling from their branches after a recent downpour. The trees densely surrounded me, and then, within a couple of steps, they were not there anymore. It was as though I had crossed an invisible boundary; the forest ended – just stopped – giving way to an abrupt, open expanse of churned-up earth. Piles of branches and stumps of felled trees lay scattered across the clearing. I found myself standing on the edge of a clear-cut, and there I began to see why it bears such a name. Not only it had created a sudden barren landscape where, over several hectares, all the trees had been felled – to the extent that, despite standing in what had once been a forest, I could easily see the horizon – but, more strikingly, to my ears gone were the layers of sound that surrounded me just moments ago. In that sensuous deafness, I set down my microphones and started an auxiliary recording. My faithful matched pair of omnidirectional mics, sheltered in a furry zeppelin, now stood on a tall tripod, imitating the only other landmarks in this desolate landscape: skeletal trunks that remained, dead or dying, a reminder of what had happened to their arboreal kin (Fig. 6). These were snags, the corpses of trees left standing as part of an ecological practice by foresters, apparently meant to mitigate some of the impacts of logging. A lone grey-headed woodpecker (*Ránesčáihni*; *Picus canus*) moving between these snags used them as lookout points, surveying the surroundings. The woodpecker let out a call that finally reattuned my ears to the surroundings, for they had felt heavy and hollow, only absorbing the absence and loss. It seemed as though the woodpecker rekindled my hearing, because from that moment, I began to detect other voices that had, until then, lain submerged by a heavy stillness. A brambling (*Vintán*; *Fringilla montifringilla*) punctuated the silence with a dry, rough trill at intervals of 10 to 15 seconds, calling from the edge of the forest across the cutting. Most notably, though, I felt disoriented by sounds that were particularly difficult to pinpoint in that desertified ground. Without the wooden walls of trees, sounds from far distances traveled easily into this barren quadrant, and the abrupt forest border enriched them with echoes that bounced from one side to the other. Standing out sharply was the clear, ringing, repetitive “tew-tew-tew” of a common greenshank (*Stuorračoavžžu*; *Tringa nebularia*) calling from a bog on the far side of the trees. A pair of late whooper swans (*Njukča*; *Cygnus cygnus*) added a brief duet, though I could not discern where it originated; they were distant, and only a faint echo reached me. Beyond these occasional bird calls, I was surprised by the total absence of mosquitoes, even near the bog. Though it is only early June, in Guovdageaidnu, I would have already needed my mosquito net for any excursion in the forest. Although I cannot claim that the place was completely silent, every sound felt strangely disconnected. They felt fragmented, mirroring the fragmentation of the landscape. And between these sounds, I could indeed find it: silence. Perhaps one of the most intense impressions I have encountered so far in my time in Sápmi. When the

bird calls were quiet all at once, I could almost perceive solely the sounds generated by my body – an experience that led John Cage to realize that absolute silence is impossible – in life. Yet, today I have found silence in Sápmi. It was in those places where the extraction of natural resources has stripped away all but a cemetery of dead trees who could left nothing to hear, but an empty acoustic space for the mourning of some birds (Audio 2).

Airvaaravägen, Vazáš

June 7, 2023, 18:30

Nicola Renzi

150 years ago, Stephen Sommier described the sonic quality of this same, albeit healthy, boreal forest as a “*silenzio di morte*” [dead silence] (Sommier 1887: 30), reducing the natural quietude of these places to a lifeless stillness. This perspective, *de facto*, reflects a dominant narrative that has for centuries associated the Arctic with a pristine emptiness, where the silence of the land is equated with the silence of its inhabitants (Grim 2001 44-45; Ligi 2016: 99-100; Ulturgasheva and Bodenhorn 2022: 27). As Ellen-Johanne Kvalsvik fittingly notes, «[h]ow you experience a silent, untouched nature is connected to ways of knowing» that starkly separate nature from culture and may lead to forms of epistemic ignorance (Kvalsvik 2019: 10; cf. Finbog 2022; Kanngieser 2023). Completely oblivious of the Sámi – who nonetheless accompanied (and served) him throughout his Arctic expedition – in his travelogue, Giuseppe Acerbi delegitimizes the history and heritage of Indigenous communities on their land, questioning the existential significance of such an emptied geographic expanse:

That profound solitude and silence which every where reigns, will every instant suggest the question, to what good end do those places serve? To what purpose all that beautiful scenery of lakes, rivers, rivulets, and cascades, if those deserts are never, as would seem to be the case, to be peopled by human beings? (Acerbi 1802: 130)

The written accounts of settlers and explorers reaching the northernmost areas of continental Europe clearly reinforced an idea of *terra nullius*, seemingly justifying settler claims to these territories (cf. Finbog 2022: 6), where the mystified emptiness was, and still is, paradoxically associated with «utterly imaginable riches» (Ulturgasheva and Bodenhorn 2022: 27). These exotifying and commodifying descriptions often relied on sublime impressions of a “vast emptiness” and “infinite silence” that, emphasizing vacuity, set the stage for extensive exploration, conquest and exploitation of the Arctic (Grim 2001; Finbog 2022; Ulturgasheva and Bodenhorn 2022; Kanngieser 2023). Consequently, these accounts underlie a dominant and pervasive history of listening to the Arctic that, in the complete absence of sounds and life, fossilized the idea of a silent North, still recently advocated by Schafer within dominant scientific frameworks. This “idea of the North” – that in Schafer delegitimizes every declination of snowmobile uses – is at the

FIGURE 6. Recording “silence” where the forest ends. Clear-cut on Airvaaravägen, Vazáš.

core of an acoustemological conquest of the region, which deliberately ignores or silences «the knowledge and cultures of Indigenous populations, of their memories and ancestral links and their manner of relating to others and to the land» (Finbog 2022: 5). Such narrative tropes as the silent North have thus contributed to a deep epistemic divide that even molded contemporary ecoacoustic scholarship, where reductive interpretations of boreal ecosystems still linger. Schafer’s mystifying perception exemplifies this, while for ecoacoustic researcher and practitioner David Monacchi,

[...] anche dopo varie escursioni verso il lontano Nord e a Vancouver Island, rimasi deluso, c’erano pochissimi suoni. [...] Il “bottino”, dal punto di vista sonoro, fu scarso, ma a quella fredda, sterminata e silenziosa foresta devo moltissimo: fu lei che mi fece definitivamente capire che in futuro avrei dovuto concentrarmi soltanto sui Tropici.²⁸ (Monacchi 2019: 47)

Through the epistemic criticalities presented by the sound of the snowmobile and the counter-narrative on silence offered by the Sámi concept of *jaskatvuohta*, I have sought to highlight how Sámi histories of listening emphasize the vitality of never-voiceless

²⁸ «[...] even after several excursions to the far North and Vancouver Island, I was disappointed – there were very few sounds. [...] The ‘loot’, from a sonic standpoint, was meager. However, I owe much to that cold, vast, and silent forest: it taught me that in the future I would need to focus solely on the Tropics».

ecosystems. From these narratives, an Indigenous acoustemology emerge where silence is solely an illusion that does not exist even where life ends – as even in its lifeless stillness, a cleared forest of skeletal trees can continue to pass down stories as long as someone is ready to listen with them.

Multimedia

Two audio recordings accompany this article. The first dates back to my initial fieldwork in Sápmi, more precisely to August 16, 2019, in Aanaar (Finnish Sápmi) during Wimme Saari's performance at the Ijahis Idja festival. It was captured using a Tascam DR-40 with its built-in microphone capsules arranged in an ORTF configuration. The second recording is a soundscape composition created from field recordings gathered during my doctoral fieldwork on June 7, 2023, in the municipality of Vazáš (Swedish Sápmi). It features sounds and silences from a clear-cut area, with echoes generated against the abrupt wall of trees marking the forest's resumption. This recording was made using a Zoom F3 with a matched pair of Primo EM272 omni-directional capsules arranged in an A-B configuration. The use of 32-bit float recording, combined with the high sensitivity of the microphones, ensured the high-fidelity capture of even the faintest sound sources.

1. Snowmobile *luohti* [1:20]

Fieldwork: Aanaar (Sápmi, Finland), 16th August 2019. Performer: Wimme Saari (juoigi).
Research and recording: Nicola Renzi

2. Excerpt from “Jaskatvuohhta ja silence”, 21st track of the audio-anthology *Muitalusat guldaleami birra – Histories of listening from Sápmi* (2025) [TBC]

Fieldwork: Vazáš municipality (Sápmi, Sweden), 7th June 2023. Soundscape composition: Nicola Renzi. Research and recording: Nicola Renzi

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